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Some tests of the binary pointing strategy
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In most of the NDAC binary simulations (for $\text{sep} < 10''$), the IDT is assumed to be pointed at the a priori (IC) photocentre of the system. As noted by FAST, this will give some bias in the photometry, because the stars will not fall symmetrically on the IDT-profile. A better alternative (for the photometry) might be instead to point at the geometrical centre of the system, thus ensuring such symmetry. In order to see how different IDT pointing strategies influence both the astrometry and the photometry, a small set of tests has been performed with the standard Lund simulation/solution software.

Three series of runs have been made, each consisting of 25 different systems observed with three different pointing strategies. The binary separation was always the maximum $10''$, the primary magnitude 8.5, and the magnitude difference 0.75, 1.5 and 2.25 in the three series (A-C). The IDT-pointing was either at the (nominal) geometrical centre, photocentre, or primary star, and the same 25 binaries (at ecliptic latitude 30 degrees) were observed with each strategy.

The results are summarized in Tables 1 and 2. Generally, the astrometric errors do not vary much with the IDT pointing. As expected, primary pointing gives a loss of accuracy for a bright secondary (Ser. A), and centre-pointing a loss of accuracy for a bright primary (Ser. C). Overall, the photocentre-pointing seems slightly preferable.

Table 1. Mean astrometric rms-values (mas, mean errors in parentheses) in the three series and for the three different pointing strategies.

	centre	photocentre	primary
rms(pr,A)	1.25 (.07)	1.14 (.06)	1.22 (.08)
rms(pr,B)	1.10 (.07)	1.08 (.07)	1.12 (.08)
rms(pr,C)	1.19 (.08)	0.95 (.07)	1.03 (.07)
rms(sec,A)	2.4 (.2)	2.4 (.2)	3.3 (.2)
rms(sec,B)	4.4 (.3)	4.0 (.2)	4.5 (.3)
rms(sec,C)	7.4 (.5)	7.4 (.4)	7.7 (.6)

Table 2. Mean magnitude errors (mean errors in parentheses) in the three series and for three different pointing strategies.

	centre	photocentre	primary
dm(pr,A)	0.049 (.006)	0.022 (.005)	0.000 (.005)
dm(pr,B)	0.044 (.004)	0.004 (.005)	-0.003 (.005)
dm(pr,C)	0.048 (.004)	0.004 (.003)	0.003 (.004)
dm(sec,A)	0.05 (.01)	0.10 (.01)	0.25 (.01)
dm(sec,B)	0.06 (.01)	0.15 (.01)	0.25 (.01)
dm(sec,C)	0.08 (.01)	0.20 (.01)	0.27 (.01)

For the magnitudes, the systematic effects are quite apparent, but still easy to understand. Pointing at the geometric centre gives a small and equal error to both components (equal to the loss of IDT sensitivity at 5 arcsec from the centre). Pointing at the primary gives zero error for the primary and the full 10 arcsec loss of sensitivity for the secondary, again independently of the magnitude difference in the system. Pointing at the photocentre gives a variable bias, reflecting the effective distance of each component from the maximum IDT sensitivity. A priori, the calibration of the photocentre bias does not seem problematic, but of course a centre or primary pointing makes the calibration easier.